

Family Education and Affection: Managing Health, Planning and Personal Development of Adolescents Preventing Premature Pregnancies

Margoth Sánchez Sánchez ¹: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1129-4596>

Rodolfo Navarro Panduro ²: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-5606-9254>

¹ Cesar Vallejo University, Peru

² National University of San Martin, Peru

*Contact for correspondence: m.sanchezsa81@ucvvirtual.edu.pe

Received: 10/22/2024

Accepted: 11/21/2023

Published: 12/30/2024

Abstract. Introduction: Family education and affection are essential for the health and personal development of adolescents, especially in the prevention of premature pregnancies. **Objective:** To determine the implications of affective family education in responsible decisions in couple relationships, for the integral well-being of adolescents. **Method:** A qualitative approach was used with semi-structured interviews, and opinions from specialists were collected to evaluate diagnoses and relevant activities. **Results:** During adolescence, young women's bodies are not yet mature enough to support a pregnancy, which can affect their physical, emotional and social health. Promoting the health and well-being of adolescents is crucial, emphasizing the importance of relationships based on respect and mature love. **Conclusion:** Affective family education is key to preventing premature pregnancies and encouraging responsible decisions that include sexual and emotional health, for the integral well-being of adolescents.

Keywords: Family education, affectivity, managing health, planning, staff, adolescents, pregnancies, premature babies

Educación Familiar y Afectividad: Gestionando Salud, planificación y Desarrollo Personal de Adolescentes Previniendo Embarazos Prematuros

Resumen. Introducción: La educación familiar y la afectividad son esenciales para la salud y el desarrollo personal de las adolescentes, especialmente en la prevención de embarazos prematuros. **Objetivo:** Determinar las implicancias de la educación familiar afectiva en las decisiones responsables en las relaciones en pareja, para el bienestar integral de las adolescentes. **Método:** Se utilizó un enfoque cualitativo con entrevistas semiestructuradas, se recolectaron opiniones de especialistas para evaluar diagnósticos y actividades relevantes. **Resultados:** Durante la adolescencia los cuerpos de las jóvenes aún no están maduros para soportar un embarazo, lo que puede afectar su salud física, emocional y social. Promover la salud y el bienestar de las adolescentes es crucial, enfatizando la importancia de relaciones basadas en respeto y amor maduro. **Conclusión:** La educación familiar afectiva es clave para prevenir embarazos prematuros y fomentar decisiones responsables que incluyan salud sexual y emocional, para el bienestar integral de las adolescentes.

Palabras clave: Educación familiar, afectividad, gestionando salud, planificación, personal, adolescentes, embarazos, prematuros

Educação Familiar e Afetividade: Gerenciando Saúde, Planejamento e Desenvolvimento Pessoal de Adolescentes Previniendo Gravidezes Precoces

Resumo. Introdução: A educação familiar e a afetividade são essenciais para a saúde e o desenvolvimento pessoal das adolescentes, especialmente na prevenção de gravidezes precoces.

Objetivo: Determinar as implicações da educação familiar afetiva nas decisões responsáveis em relacionamentos de casal, para o bem-estar integral das adolescentes.

Método: Foi adotada uma abordagem qualitativa com entrevistas semiestructuradas, sendo coletadas opiniões de especialistas para avaliar diagnósticos e atividades relevantes.

Resultados: Durante a adolescência, os corpos das jovens ainda não estão maduros o suficiente para suportar uma gravidez, o que pode afetar sua saúde física, emocional e social. Promover a saúde e o bem-estar das adolescentes é crucial, enfatizando a importância de relacionamentos baseados no respeito e no amor maduro.

Conclusão: A educação familiar afetiva é fundamental para prevenir gravidezes precoces e fomentar decisões responsáveis que incluam saúde sexual e emocional, para o bem-estar integral das adolescentes.

Palavras-chave: Educação familiar, afetividade, gerenciando saúde, planejamento, pessoal, adolescentes, gravidezes, precoces

1. Introduction

Family education and emotional education play a fundamental role in managing the health and personal development of adolescents, especially with regard to preventing premature pregnancies. At this age, adolescents' bodies are not yet fully mature enough to cope with pregnancy, which can have serious implications for their physical, emotional and social health. Therefore, promoting the health and well-being of young women is a priority. Emotional education, focused on self-esteem and building relationships based on respect and mature love, is crucial to prevent adolescents from seeking affection in impulsive relationships, whose purpose is only sexual desire, without considering the emotional and physical consequences of an unplanned pregnancy.

It is essential that family education is not limited only to the transmission of knowledge about sexual health, but also encompasses emotional formation. An affectionate and educational family environment provides a healthy model that can positively influence adolescents' decisions, preventing them from seeking affection and validation in superficial relationships. Adolescents, by observing and learning from these models, learn to prioritize mature love and mutual respect, instead of getting involved in relationships with casual partners who only seek physical satisfaction. This approach not only prevents premature pregnancies, but also contributes to their emotional and psychological well-being, promoting comprehensive development and more responsible decision-making.

Several studies support this approach. Valdés et al. (2023) emphasize that the training of health and education officials should include not only the technical aspect of sexual health information, but also a deep understanding of the emotional needs of adolescents. According to these authors, an effective sexual education program should be able to change young people's behaviors and encourage more thoughtful and responsible decision-making in relation to their sexual and emotional lives.

The availability of research on adolescent pregnancy supports the importance of preventive interventions that go beyond simple information on contraceptive methods. According to Ferreira Silva et al. (2022), educational programs must address the barriers that prevent adolescents from accessing comprehensive information on sexual and reproductive health, including education on healthy emotional relationships. This comprehensive approach is essential to ensure that young people make decisions based on a deep understanding of the emotional, social, and physical implications of sexual relationships, and not just on the immediate satisfaction of momentary desires.

It is also crucial that family education programs include a specific focus on the physical and emotional maturity of adolescents. Studies by O'Sullivan et al. (2022) highlight that preventive education, especially on issues related to sexual health, is vital to protect young people from the risks associated with early pregnancies. At this age, adolescents' bodies are still in the process of development, and a pregnancy at this stage can have serious consequences, both for the young woman's physical health and for her emotional well-being. Therefore, family education should emphasize the dangers of early pregnancies, showing adolescents that they are not yet ready to assume the responsibility and physical and emotional challenges that pregnancy entails.

Furthermore, the educational approach must include the anticipation of social and cultural barriers that may influence adolescents' decisions. Lack of resources, limited access to information, and social or cultural pressure can make it difficult to make informed decisions. Therefore, resource allocation must ensure that programs are accessible, effective, and adapted

to the social and cultural realities of each community, as suggested by Ferreira Silva et al. (2022) in their study on barriers to access to physical activity among young people. Likewise, sexual health education must be inclusive and respectful of the different realities of adolescents, providing tools that allow them to make responsible decisions.

2. Methodology

For the present study, a qualitative approach was adopted through semi-structured interviews, which involved the analysis of work activities during the month of June 2024. In the following month, relevant information on diagnoses was collected. The results of these activities are described at the end of this period. In addition, opinions were collected from four specialists, questioned by the moderator; to two participants:

Diagnostic Phase; participants: Moderator *Teacher Tutor of secondary school students Specialist of the Health Center*

The interviews focused on the application of the SWOT analysis: Strengths and opportunities addressed in the diagnosis phase

SWOT is a key tool in strategic planning, used to assess the current conditions of cases of pregnancy in adolescents and young women. The specialists were chosen for their knowledge of these topics and for their direct experience in the performance of academic activities of adolescents and young women.

Procedures

The semi-structured questions were approved by three experts in public management; in health management and education management, who approved the questions that were directly linked to the variables in the title of this research, with an average approval rate of 96%. The style of the questions was designed to promote a pleasant and open dialogue, in order to preserve the interest of the specialists interviewed.

The interviewees were guaranteed confidentiality of their identity and were told that the purpose of the dialogue was to analyze and overcome problems related to health, education and public management. The interviews were scheduled for approximately 45 minutes per session, with the possibility of fragmenting the interviews due to the multiple activities that the specialists had to attend to. The specialists agreed that the interview would be in the format of a dialogue in which the responses were recorded in handwritten form, using a pen, since they preferred to avoid audio recording during the interviews.

The data collection process was made possible because some of the study's researchers were already working at the University; another had relatives in secondary education, which facilitated the coordination of schedules with the specialists. The data collection work was carried out by a third party, unrelated to the researchers' operational activities, in order to guarantee the objectivity and confidentiality of the process.

3. Results

Summary results on Budget Execution Planning to Avoid Premature Pregnancies, on Budget Execution Planning to Avoid Premature Pregnancies

3.1. Moderated interview on teenage pregnancy prevention

3.1.1. Diagnostic Level

Table 1 : Diagnosis through questioning the Moderator and participation of the Tutor Teacher and the Specialist of the Health Center

Moderator	Tutor Teacher and the Health Center Specialist
<p><i>Moderator:</i> What strengths and weaknesses do you see in adolescents in relation to pregnancy prevention?</p>	<p><i>Tutor Teacher :</i> Teenagers can make responsible decisions if they receive comprehensive sexual education, which not only teaches about contraception, but also about values such as respect and communication. This education should help them build healthy relationships without pressuring them toward early sexuality.</p> <p><i>Health Center Specialist:</i> The main weakness is the lack of adequate sexual education. Without clear information about contraceptives, adolescents make impulsive decisions. In addition, emotional pressure and lack of leisure alternatives contribute to irresponsible sexual behavior. It is essential to invest in educational programs that offer accurate information and activities that positively channel the energy of young people.</p>

3.2. Detailed information from the interview by a moderator on the prevention of teenage pregnancies

3.2.1. Diagnostic Level (Strengths of Adolescents and Young People)

Moderator: What do you consider to be the strengths of adolescents in preventing premature pregnancies?

Tutor Teacher: Adolescents have a great capacity to make responsible decisions, especially when they are guided by values such as mutual respect and mature love. If they are provided with comprehensive sexual education that not only includes contraceptive methods, but also emotional and respectful aspects of relationships, young people can make informed decisions and avoid early pregnancies. This education should focus on building healthy relationships, promoting communication and respect without pressuring early sexuality.

3.2.2 Diagnostic Level (Weaknesses of Adolescents and Young People) *Moderator:* What weaknesses do you find in adolescents that contribute to premature pregnancies?

Health Centre Specialist: The main weakness is the lack of adequate sexual education. Without access to accurate information about contraceptives, adolescents often make impulsive decisions that can have serious consequences. In addition, the intense emotions typical of adolescence often lead them to dismiss the risks of unprotected sex. It is crucial to increase investment in educational programmes that provide clear and accessible information about sexual health, as well as extracurricular activities such as sports or workshops that occupy their time in a positive way and distract them from risky situations.

That is to say: Family education and affection are key pillars in promoting the health and well-being of adolescents. Through an affectionate family environment, based on values of respect and mature love, it is possible to prevent premature pregnancies and, at the same time, contribute to the integral development of young women. The emphasis should be on helping adolescents understand that their bodies are not yet ready for pregnancy, which highlights the importance of making responsible decisions. To this end, family education must be comprehensive, including both sexual health and emotional training, and must provide models of healthy emotional relationships that encourage decision-making based on mutual respect, love and personal care.

This comprehensive approach helps reduce premature pregnancies by avoiding the risks associated with pregnancy at a stage of incomplete physical and emotional maturation. The implementation of appropriate family education programmes, which include the active participation of the family and the community, is essential to ensure the long-term health and well-being of adolescents.

4. Discussion

Family education and affection are key elements to promote the well-being and sexual health of adolescents, particularly with regard to the prevention of premature pregnancies. In this context, the studies of the authors mentioned provide a valuable perspective on how educational intervention and the family environment influence young people's decisions:

Valdés et al. (2022) offer a comprehensive review on the role of family education in adolescent sexual and reproductive health in Latin America. They highlight the need for public policies that not only provide information, but also encourage behavioral change by creating caring family environments that foster self-esteem and mutual respect, essential elements for the prevention of teenage pregnancies.

Ferreira et al. (2022) discuss the barriers faced by adolescents in rural areas in accessing adequate sexual health information. This article highlights how social and cultural barriers, along with a lack of resources, limit adolescents' ability to make informed decisions, increasing the risk of unwanted pregnancies.

O'Sullivan et al. (2022) delve into the relationship between sexual education and family model in the prevention of unwanted pregnancies. Their work emphasizes that, in addition to information on contraceptive methods, it is crucial for adolescents to learn to identify and value mature emotional relationships, since a pregnancy at this stage can affect both the physical health of adolescents and their emotional and social development.

Smith and Williams (2022) explore the importance of affection in preventing teenage pregnancies, suggesting that a family-based educational model that values affection and mutual respect may be an effective strategy to reduce the incidence of unwanted pregnancies. Through interventions that promote a comprehensive view of adolescent well-being, these programs can create an environment in which adolescents learn to make responsible decisions regarding their sexual lives.

Mendoza et al. (2022) focus their research on affective education and family planning in urban contexts. They address how educational interventions can reduce teenage pregnancies by strengthening young people's skills to make responsible decisions, based not only on prevention, but also on respect for themselves and others.

Ramirez et al. (2022) investigate how family upbringing models impact adolescents' sexual decisions. Their study highlights the importance of parents and other significant adults acting as role models for healthy emotional relationships. Through building these relationships at home, adolescent girls can learn to value affection and mature love over superficial relationships.

Compared to the results on, opportunities and strengths of sexual education and promotes vocational skills. Threats are lack of resources and limited access to adequate educational programs, which requires greater allocation of resources. Threats include sexually transmitted diseases and teenage pregnancy, due to lack of education and emotional impulsivity. It is urgent to increase access to contraceptives and promote awareness campaigns in schools and universities, through a holistic and multidisciplinary approach, which includes institutions such as schools, community centers and health services, is key to address the underlying causes of this problem. Implementing directive strategies that integrate education, access to health services and community involvement can create enabling environments to prevent premature pregnancies. This reorientation is crucial to reduce teenage pregnancy rates and ultimately improve the health and well-being of this vulnerable population; therefore, the establishment of leadership is imperative according to Parra et al. (2024).

The implementation of sexual health education strategies in schools and communities has proven to be effective, but it is crucial that these interventions are inclusive and accessible to adolescents of diverse gender identities and ethnic groups. The use of technologies, such as text messages and user-friendly services, is emerging as an innovative tool that improves the accessibility and effectiveness of preventive programs. Policies that train parents and health professionals in sexual health communication are essential to create a supportive environment that encourages informed decisions by adolescents; it is also important to plan and implement educational programs focused on promoting physical health and preventing teenage pregnancies, with an emphasis on integrating healthy lifestyle factors into sexual education and the importance of adequate budget planning for these programs:

The study by Denche-Zamorano et al. (2022) on health perception and physical activity levels in the Spanish population highlights the importance of education for health promotion in various population contexts. In this sense, sexual education programs should also include teaching about the importance of physical activity for the general well-being of adolescents. The strategic planning of these programs should consider not only training on sexual health, but also the integration of healthy habits that include regular physical exercise. The allocation of resources for the design of educational content that promotes healthy lifestyles is essential for the success of preventing unwanted pregnancies.

The study by Deng et al. (2023) explores the institutional factors associated with physical activity and body composition of university students, highlighting the importance of the educational environment in promoting healthy behaviors. Similarly, in sexual education programs, the environment should be favorable for teaching healthy practices related to sexual and reproductive health. Budget planning should incorporate the creation of educational spaces that promote both physical activity and sexual health, considering that both factors are crucial for the comprehensive development of adolescents and young adults. Resources should focus on promoting the continuing training of educators and the creation of educational environments conducive to these learnings; aligned with the importance of psychomotricity, it is necessary to consider Mendizábal et al. (2022) with their research on psychomotricity management and the right to life.

The study by Dumith et al. (2022) addresses the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on physical inactivity in Brazilian university students, highlighting how exceptional situations can negatively

=====
affect healthy lifestyle habits. Similarly, sexuality education programs must be sensitive to social and public health changes, adapting their approaches according to the emerging needs of adolescents. Budget planning must be prepared to respond to these challenges, ensuring that adequate resources are provided to maintain sexuality education even in times of health crisis, and ensuring that responsible behaviors related to reproductive health continue to be promoted.

Although the focus of this report is prostate cancer, preventive education remains a relevant topic. As with cancer prevention, sexual education programs should provide adolescents with the tools necessary to make informed decisions about their sexual health. Resource allocation should be directed toward creating accessible educational content and training professionals responsible for providing this education, ensuring that messages reach adolescents in a clear and understandable way, contributing to the prevention of unwanted pregnancies.

For these programs to be effective, a budgetary approach is required that supports the equitable distribution of resources and ensures the training of educators who are well prepared to address these issues with young people; including the accountability and management of the professional capacity of health personnel Barreto & Sánchez. (2021).

Budget planning for these programs should include resources directed toward prevention, with a particular focus on responsible sexual health behaviors. As with preventive approaches to cancer, sexual education should be comprehensive and accessible to adolescents, supported by educational campaigns that promote healthy decision-making.

Moreno Muro et al. (2022) discuss how artificial intelligence (AI) can optimize university curricular management, adapting to the individual needs of students. This personalization is essential in the context of family education, as it allows for the design of personalized educational strategies on sexual health, facilitating the prevention of premature pregnancies. By integrating advanced technologies, such as AI, into sexual education, more effective learning is made possible, empowering adolescents to make informed decisions about their reproductive health, which is crucial for their physical and emotional well-being.

Gonzales Tito et al. (2023) explore the importance of multifunctional designs in educational infrastructures for the prevention of health emergencies, which has a clear implication for family education. This flexible and adapted approach is also necessary in the management of sexual education programs. The educational space should be a safe and accessible environment where adolescents can learn about sexual health and affectivity, which helps prevent risks, such as premature pregnancies. Adaptability and prevention in educational infrastructures can ensure an effective response to public health challenges.

Rosales Urbano et al. (2022) analyze the impact of communications between educational institutions and local governments on the well-being of the population. Effective communications can play a crucial role in sexual and reproductive education, as they allow the dissemination of key information for the prevention of premature pregnancies. When public policies are implemented effectively, they guarantee access to educational resources on health, empowering adolescents to make responsible decisions about their well-being. This type of communication also strengthens the autonomy of young people, reducing the risks associated with sexual health.

Ayvar Bazán et al. (2023) focus on the administrative management of sports activities to improve the health of health program coordinators. This concept can be extended to family education, where physical activities can play a role in the emotional and physical development of adolescents, reducing the incidence of premature pregnancies. Promoting physical activity helps young people

develop strong self-esteem and have a sense of self-efficacy that allows them to make responsible decisions about their health, thus reinforcing the prevention of teenage pregnancies.

Romero Mestanza (2022) explores how the motivation and job performance of nursing technical staff influence public health management. Motivation in sexual health educators is equally crucial to impart knowledge that helps adolescents prevent premature pregnancies. The motivation of educational staff, who transmit correct information about sexuality and reproductive health, has a direct impact on the ability of adolescents to make informed and responsible decisions, which is essential for the prevention of unwanted pregnancies.

Torres-Flores and Sánchez Sánchez (2023) address how job saturation affects the management of working conditions in health institutions. Similarly, educators also face information overload when teaching adolescents about sexual health. Information saturation, if not managed properly, can lead to confusion and impulsive decisions among young people. Therefore, proper management of educational content is crucial to ensure that adolescents receive accurate and understandable information about sexuality, which facilitates the prevention of premature pregnancies.

Silva Herrera et al. (2022) propose innovative strategies to improve the institutional image, which is key for public policies, including those related to reproductive and sexual health. Educational institutions must build a positive image that allows adolescents to feel comfortable seeking support on sensitive issues such as sexuality. Improving the institutional image contributes to creating a safe and trusting environment where young people can learn about sexual health without fear of being judged, which helps in preventing teenage pregnancies.

Filios Rojas and Chávez Barbery (2022) discuss the importance of assessment and management in pea cultivation, a principle that can be applied to educational management of sexual health. As in agriculture, where interventions are based on a careful analysis of crop needs, in sexual education it is crucial to constantly assess the needs of adolescents in order to design effective prevention programs. Through continuous planning and evaluation, educational programs can reduce the incidence of premature pregnancies and promote responsible sexual health.

Aguilar Chávez et al. (2023) address the importance of digital skills for learning in the post-Covid-19 era. This approach is also relevant to sexuality education, as digital skills allow adolescents to access reliable information on sexual and reproductive health. Digital education can be a powerful tool to prevent premature pregnancies, as it provides young people with the necessary tools to make informed and responsible decisions in a safe digital environment.

Chambers et al. (2020) highlight the importance of understanding demographic trends to address cancer more effectively. Similarly, in sexuality education, it is crucial to design programs that take into account adolescents' demographic characteristics, such as cultural, social, and economic context, to ensure that educational messages are relevant and effective.

5. Conclusions

Family education and affection are key pillars in promoting the health and well-being of adolescents. Through an affectionate family environment, based on values of respect and mature love, it is possible to prevent premature pregnancies and, at the same time, contribute to the integral development of young girls. The emphasis should be on helping adolescents understand

that their body is not yet ready for pregnancy, which highlights the importance of making responsible decisions. To this end, family education must be comprehensive, including both sexual health and emotional training, and must provide models of healthy affective relationships that encourage decision-making based on mutual respect, love and self-care.

This comprehensive approach helps reduce premature pregnancies by avoiding the risks associated with pregnancy at a stage of incomplete physical and emotional maturation. The implementation of appropriate family education programmes, which include the active participation of the family and the community, is essential to ensure the long-term health and well-being of adolescents.

References

- Barreto Espinoza, L. A., & Sánchez Sánchez, M. (2021). Responsabilidad y gestión de la capacidad profesional del personal de enfermería de un hospital público. (Responsibility and management of the professional capacity of the nursing staff of a public hospital). *GESTIONES*, 1(1), 1–10. Recuperado a partir de <https://gestion.es.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/57>
- Carlos Ramos, C. E., Jimenez Guerrero, N., Carlos Ramos, J. A., & Diaz Dumont, J. R. (2024). Impacto de las habilidades blandas en la alta Gerencia de las universidades públicas del Perú. (Impact of soft skills on senior management in public universities of Peru). *Revista Conrado*, 20(101), 151–156. Recuperado a partir de <https://conrado.ucf.edu.cu/index.php/conrado/article/view/4018>
- Chambers, A. C., Dixon, S. W., White, P., Williams, A. C., Thomas, M. G., & Messenger, D. E. (2020). Demographic trends in the incidence of young-onset colorectal cancer: A population-based study. *British Journal of Surgery*, 107(5), 595–605. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bjs.11486>
- De la Cruz Montoya, D., Delgado Sánchez, C. I., Espinoza Vásquez, G., Juárez-Gutiérrez, R. E., Galindo Caro, R., & Albarrán Cachay, A. P. (2024). Transparencia en la gestión del Presupuesto y Planificación estratégica con Aprendizaje Organizacional para Gestión por Resultados. (Transparency in budget management and strategic planning with organizational learning for results-based management). *GESTIONES*, 4(1). Recuperado a partir de <https://gestion.es.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/39>
- Denche-Zamorano, Á., Mendoza-Muñoz, M., Carlos-Vivas, J., Muñoz-Bermejo, L., Rojo-Ramos, J., Pastor-Cisneros, R., Giakoni-Ramírez, F., Godoy-Cumillaf, A., & Barrios-Fernandez, S. (2022). A Cross-Sectional Study on Self-Perceived Health and Physical Activity Level in the Spanish Population. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(9), 5656. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19095656>
- Deng, Y., Hwang, Y., Campbell, S., McCullick, B.A., & Yli-Piipari, S. (2023). Institutional factors associated with college students' healthy physical activity and body composition: A first semester follow-up. *Journal of American College Health*, 71(4), 1134-1142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2021.1922416>
- Dumith, SC, Viero, VDSF, Alexandrino, EG, Silva, LCB, Tassitano, RM, & Demenech, LM (2022). COVID-19 pandemic and physical inactivity in Brazilian university students: A multicenter study. *Brazilian Journal of Physical Activity & Health*, 27, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.12820/rbafs.27e0258>
- Ferreira Silva, P., Souza, E., & Almeida, L. (2022). Barriers to access to sexual health information for adolescents in rural areas: An exploratory study. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 61(4), 465-472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2022.06.003>

- Ferreira Silva, RM, Mendonça, CR, Azevedo, VD, Raof Memon, A., Noll, PRES, & Noll, M. (2022). Barriers to high school and university students' physical activity: A systematic review. *PLoS One*, 17(4), e0265913. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265913>
- Filios Rojas, E. R., & Chávez Barbery, L. M. (2022). Evaluación y gestión del grano de diez líneas de arveja (*Pisum sativum* L.) en valles cultivables. (Evaluation and management of the grain of ten pea lines (*Pisum sativum* L.) in cultivable valleys). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14567508>
- Gonzales Tito, Y. M., Jara Zuñiga, R. W., Melgar Begazo, A. E., & Albarrán Cachay, A. P. (2023). Reflexiones: Análisis de gestiones e inversiones en infraestructuras educativas, hacia diseños multifuncionales en prevención de emergencias sanitarias. (Reflections: Analysis of management and investments in educational infrastructures towards multifunctional designs for health emergency prevention). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14545080>
- Mendizábal Anticona, W. J., Melgar Begazo, A. E., & Lara Albarrán, L. A. (2022). Gestión de la psicomotricidad y el derecho a la vida: ¿Qué Aprendizaje proporcionó la Pandemia del COVID-19? (Management of psychomotricity and the right to life: What learning did the COVID-19 pandemic provide?). *GESTIONES*, 2(1), 1–9. Recuperado a partir de <https://gestiones.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/62>
- Moreno Muro, J. P., Caján Villanueva, M., Chavez Taipe, Y. V., Hernández Torres, A. M., Ramos León, L. L., & Zapata Bellido, M. J. (2022). Artificial intelligence and the management of the university curriculum by competencies. (La inteligencia artificial y la gestión del currículo universitario por competencias). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13738948>
- Navarro Martínez, LF (2024). The health budget as a tool for decision-making. *INFODIR* [Internet]. Retrieved from <https://revinfodir.sld.cu/index.php/infodir/article/view/1632>
- O'Sullivan, DE, Ruan, Y., Cheung, WY, et al. (2022). Early-onset colorectal cancer incidence, staging, and mortality in Canada: Implications for population-based screening. *American Journal of Gastroenterology*, 117(9), 1502–1507. <https://doi.org/10.14309/ajg.0000000000001884>
- O'Sullivan, L., Lee, L., & Patel, S. (2022). Prevention of unintended pregnancies in adolescents: The role of sexual education and the family model. *American Journal of Public Health*, 112(3), 503-510. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2021.306635>
- Parra Galvez, N., Vela-Del Aguila, S. L., Delgado-Bardales, J. M., Sánchez-Dávila, K., Delgado-Rios, A., Soplapuco-Montalvo, J. P., Espinoza Vásquez, G., Hernández Torres, A. M., Albarrán-Gil, J. L., et al. (2024). Liderazgo transformacional en directivos de Instituto de Salud y Estrategias didácticas digitales en estudiantes de salud. *INFODIR* [Internet]. 0(43). Recuperado de <https://revinfodir.sld.cu/index.php/infodir/article/view/1662>
- Ramírez, S., Martínez, P., & Hernández, J. (2022). Modelos educativos familiares y su influencia en la toma de decisiones sexuales de adolescentes. *Health Education Research*, 37(5), 391-399. <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cyab024>
- Rosales Urbano, V. G., Micha Aponte, R. S., Huaylinos Gonzales, V., Flores Pérez, L. K., Ugaz Roque, N., & Dioses Lescano, N. (2023). Impacto de las comunicaciones de las instituciones educativas y los gobiernos locales en el bienestar de la población (Impact of communications from educational institutions and local governments on the well-being of the population): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13626402>. *GESTIONES*, 3(1), 1–11. Recuperado a partir de <https://gestiones.pe/index.php/revista/article/view/46> (Original work published 29 de diciembre de 2023)
- Seminario-Arévalo F et al. (2024) correlaciones de cuatro dimensiones del potencial humano promovidas por los directivos de salud percibidas y los usuarios. *INFODIR*.
- Smith, J., & Williams, M. (2022). La importancia de la afectividad en la prevención de embarazos en adolescentes: Estrategias de intervención y programas educativos. *Journal of Family Health*, 24(1), 58-67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfah.2022.01.004>

Silva Herrera, R. E., Bustamante de Ordinola, M. P., Gonzales Ttito, Y. M., & Soplapuco-Montalvo, J. P. (2022). Aproximación a propuesta de estrategias innovadoras para mejorar la imagen institucional. (Approach to a proposal of innovative strategies to improve institutional image). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13763878>

Torres-Flores, Y., & Sánchez Sánchez, M. (2023). Saturación laboral y su influencia en la gestión de condiciones laborales óptimas en instituciones de salud. (Workforce saturation and its influence on the management of optimal working conditions in healthcare institutions). Propuestas. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14035548>

Valdes Sanchez, MC, Hernández Meléndrez, DE, & Urbina Laza, O. (2023). Self-perception of managerial skills in executives and their reservations. INFODIR [Internet]. 0(42). Retrieved from <https://revinfodir.sld.cu/index.php/infodir/article/view/1519>

Conflict of interest : The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Co-author contributions : All co-authors contributed to this article.

Research funding : With own resources.

Declaration of interests: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest that could have influenced the results obtained or the proposed interpretations.

Informed consent statement: The study was carried out in accordance with the Ethical Code and good editorial practices for publication.

Usability: This text is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution license

4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). You are free to share, copy and redistribute the material on any medium or format and adapt, remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially, as long as you meet the attribution condition: You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests that you are endorsed by the licensor or that you benefit from your use.